

Interactive Visual Correction of Dynamic Time Warping Alignments

Harsh Dange

Shapour Hakam

Sepideh Shafiei

Abstract—Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) is widely used to align time series that differ in temporal structure. Although DTW provides an optimal alignment under a given cost function, it often produces locally incorrect correspondences when signals differ substantially or contain noise, missing segments, or structural deviations. We introduce an interactive visual tool that allows users to iteratively correct DTW alignments by inserting anchor correspondences between two signals. Each anchor constrains the alignment and triggers segmented recomputation of DTW before and after the selected points. The method enables efficient human-in-the-loop refinement of time-series alignments and can be applied across domains. We illustrate the approach with an example application to aligning audio and MIDI representations of vocal musical performances. The implementation of the proposed tool is open-source and available at <https://github.com/hsd2514/DTWcorrectionInterface>. This method can also reduce computational cost, especially for higher-order DTW algorithms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) is a classical algorithm for aligning time-dependent sequences that may vary in speed or temporal structure. It has been applied in many domains including speech processing [1], [2], and music information retrieval [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8].

In many real-world scenarios, purely automatic DTW alignment can produce locally incorrect correspondences, some of which are critical to identify and correct in order to accurately reflect the underlying structure of the data. To address this issue, we propose an interactive visual correction tool that allows users to guide the alignment process. Instead of relying exclusively on automatic optimization, the system allows users to iteratively insert anchor correspondences between the two signals. The alignment is then recomputed in segments that respect these constraints. This approach provides a flexible human-in-the-loop mechanism for correcting DTW alignments with minimal manual effort.

The motivation for this work emerged from practical challenges encountered while aligning Midi and Audio signals for vocal music. As musicians and music engravers working with automatically generated symbolic representations, we frequently needed to align audio recordings with symbolic transcriptions in order to verify and refine the results. While Dynamic Time Warping

provides a useful automatic alignment, we found that small local misalignments required manual correction. Performing these corrections directly is difficult and time-consuming, motivating the development of the interactive visual tool presented in this paper.

II. METHOD

The system takes two time-series signals as input:

- Signal $S_1 = (s_1^1, s_1^2, \dots, s_1^n)$
- Signal $S_2 = (s_2^1, s_2^2, \dots, s_2^m)$

To illustrate the method, we consider two signals: one corresponding to a vocal audio recording and the other to a modified MIDI ¹ representation of the same recording. We focus on a small segment of each signal to allow the reader to clearly observe the effect of the proposed method. The selected segment includes a plateau and a peak, making the expected alignment visually apparent to a human observer.

Fig. 1. Initial sample signals S_1 and S_2

A standard DTW alignment is first computed between the two sequences, producing a correspondence path through the DTW cost matrix.

A. Alignment Visualization

The resulting alignment is visualized as a mapping between the time axes of the two signals. This visualization allows users to inspect whether the alignment follows the expected relationship between the signals. A human observer can immediately see that the plateau and the

¹Iranian classical vocal music features a characteristic ornamentation known as tahrir [9]. The MIDI representations are refined to capture this specific ornamentation.

peak in the two signals are not correctly aligned, even though the DTW algorithm achieves the global minimum cost for this alignment under the given constraints.

The lower window displays the alignment error at each point along the alignment path between the two signals. This visualization serves both as a demonstration and as a diagnostic tool for identifying regions where the alignment error is high.

Fig. 2. Initial DTW alignment of S_1 and S_2

B. Anchor Selection

After the user visually detects a DTW mismatch, for example in the case of S_1 and S_2 where a peak in one signal is not aligned with the corresponding peak in the other despite the correct alignment being visually apparent, they can select two points by clicking on a point in S_1 and the corresponding point in S_2 . These points define a desired correspondence, referred to as an *anchor*. Figure 3 shows the anchor selection for the two signals S_1 and S_2 .

Fig. 3. Anchor selection on S_1 and S_2

C. Segmented DTW Recalculation

After selecting an anchor point, we recompute the DTW alignment so that the resulting correspondence between the two signals satisfies the user-defined anchor. Let the anchor be the pair $(i \in S_1, j \in S_2)$. The signals are then divided into two regions: the segments before the anchor and the segments after the anchor. DTW is recomputed independently on these two segments while

enforcing the anchor constraint. This produces a revised alignment path. For our example, the new DTW path is shown in Figure 4. As can be seen from the revised path, the peak and the plateau of the two signals are now aligned as desired.

Fig. 4. Improved DTW alignment of S_1 and S_2

D. Iterative Refinement

Users may insert additional anchors wherever misalignments remain. Each anchor partitions the signals into smaller segments, progressively refining the alignment. In practice, only a small number of anchors is typically required to obtain satisfactory results. Multiple anchor pairs can also be specified simultaneously, which can significantly reduce computational cost, especially for higher-order DTW versions.

III. EXAMPLE APPLICATION: AUDIO-MIDI ALIGNMENT

One application of the tool is aligning symbolic and audio representations of music. For example, a MIDI transcription of a performance can be aligned with the corresponding audio recording using feature sequences derived from each representation.

Expressive timing, ornamentation, and transcription inaccuracies can cause standard DTW to produce locally incorrect alignments. Using the proposed tool, a user can visually inspect the alignment graph and insert anchors at key musical events (such as note onsets or phrase boundaries). The alignment is then recomputed in constrained segments, producing a corrected correspondence between the MIDI and audio signals.

Although this example comes from music information retrieval, the method itself is general and can be applied to any domain where DTW-based alignment requires interactive refinement.

IV. DISCUSSION

The proposed system augments DTW with a lightweight interactive correction mechanism. Rather than replacing automatic alignment algorithms, the method provides a structured way for users to guide the optimization process when necessary.

This approach can significantly reduce the effort required for manual alignment while maintaining high-quality correspondences. It is particularly useful in domains where expert visual inspection can easily identify alignment errors that are difficult to capture with automated cost functions.

Future work may explore automatic suggestions for anchor points, integration with alternative alignment algorithms, and domain-specific visualization strategies.

V. CONCLUSION

We introduced an interactive visual tool for correcting DTW alignments between time-series signals. By allowing users to insert anchor correspondences and recompute DTW on segmented regions, the method enables efficient human-in-the-loop refinement of alignments. The approach is general and applicable across domains, with audio-MIDI alignment serving as one example application.

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